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Marine Soundscape as an additional biodiversity monitoring tool: a case study from the Adriatic Sea (Mediterranean Sea)

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18 **Abstract**

19 Acoustic monitoring can provide essential information on marine environments, including insights
20 into ecosystem functioning and marine biodiversity monitoring. However, data on species acoustic
21 behavior and ecoacoustics studies in the Mediterranean Sea are still extremely scarce and this limits
22 our ability to use soundscape features in monitoring studies. Here we present the results of a
23 soundscape investigation conducted on shallow hard bottoms of the Adriatic Sea (Central
24 Mediterranean basin). We report the presence of diverse circadian rhythms recorded in two
25 different months, July and September. A power spectral density (PSD) was used to assess the overall
26 spectral composition over time, and the Acoustic Complexity Index (ACI), was identified as a proxy
27 for marine sounds of biological origin. The dominant component of the biological soundscape was
28 composed of snapping shrimps and fishes. Spectral characteristics varied significantly both daily and
29 between the two months. For frequencies >620 Hz (i.e., associated to snapping shrimp activity),
30 both PSD and ACI were higher in July than in September. The same circadian rhythm was reported
31 in both sampling periods, with the presence of snaps for 24h a day, but with significantly lower
32 intensity during daylight hours and pitches at the beginning and ending of the night. At lower
33 frequencies (i.e., <620 Hz), fish vocalizations mostly occurred during the night. Higher values of ACI
34 were recorded during the night in both months, whereas the presence of anthropogenic noise
35 caused opposite results in PSD levels. Noise was associated with higher PSD and ACI at the peak
36 frequency of the snaps, suggesting a stimulation in snapping activity. Our findings provide new
37 insights on the marine biological soundscape and on the potential use of ecoacoustics in future
38 monitoring programs.

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40

41 **Keywords:** marine environmental monitoring, fish vocalizations, snapping shrimp, soundscape,
42 ecoacoustics, Mediterranean Sea

43

1. Introduction

Ecoacoustics is an emerging discipline, which is providing novel and promising outcomes for the exploration of the functional biodiversity (Sueur and Farina, 2015) and characterization of marine ecosystems (Harris et al., 2015). It investigates the 'soundscape' that can be defined as the aggregation of sounds from physical (wind, waves, etc.), biological (sounds produced by animals), and anthropogenic (vessels, ports, roads, etc.) sources. The three sound sources are known as geophony, biophony and technophony, respectively (Farina, 2014 p.3; Gage and Axel, 2014; Krause, 1987; Mullet et al., 2016; Pijanowski et al., 2011).

While both light and chemical cues are effective at small spatial scales (over very short distances, i.e., cm-m), sounds travel fast through water (about $1,500 \text{ m s}^{-1}$; Urick, 1984) and are capable of conveying significant information over considerable distances. Given the importance of sound transmission in seawater (almost five times higher than in the air) and the generally limited transparency of marine waters, marine species use sounds for numerous different functional processes (Urick, 1984; van Opzeeland and Slabbekoorn, 2012). Several species, from marine mammals to fishes, and invertebrates use sounds for their foraging (Versluis et al., 2000), navigation (Slabbekoorn and Bouton, 2008), predation and detection of predators, communication, reproduction (Mann and Lobel, 1997) and habitat selection (Simpson, 2005). Sounds in marine habitats are thus fundamental for the life cycle of marine animals.

For this reason, the collection and analysis of acoustic signals have been recently proposed as a tool to evaluating the specific features of ecological assemblages and to monitoring their acoustic dynamics over space and time (Sueur and Farina, 2015). Unlike traditional surveys of marine biodiversity, which are typically invasive, discrete and potentially affected by human presence, acoustic records can be collected without human presence, twenty-four hours a day, over long times and also under adverse meteorological conditions. Moreover, recently the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC) (MSFD) identified underwater noise within the 11 descriptors of environmental quality (Tasker et al., 2008). Anthropogenic noise indeed, masking marine biological signals, can pose a potential threat to marine assemblages affecting behavior and communication of a wide array of marine animals (Clark et al., 2009; Codarin et al., 2009; Filiciotto et al., 2014, 2016;

75 Slabbekoorn et al., 2010; Tyack, 2008). However, the lack of data on the natural biological
76 soundscape hampers the evaluation of the actual impact of noise on marine assemblages.

77

78 In marine and terrestrial habitats, sounds can fluctuate over daily and seasonal time scales (Cato
79 and McCauley, 2002; Lobel et al., 2010) creating peculiar soundscape signatures, defined as the
80 main acoustic features of the soundscapes (*sensu* Farina et al., 2011). A soundscape signature
81 potentially distinguishes every habitat type, through the description of the specific properties of the
82 collected sounds (Bertucci et al., 2015). Preliminary descriptions of marine soundscapes are now
83 available for locations in the Pacific (Andrew et al., 2002; Bertucci et al., 2015; Staaterman et al.,
84 2013), Atlantic (Axelrod et al., 1965; Staaterman et al., 2013; Urick et al., 1972), Indian Oceans (Cato,
85 1976; McCauley, 2011; Parsons et al., 2013) and for the Mediterranean Sea (Buscaino et al., 2016).

86 Bioacoustics studies have been performed in the Mediterranean Sea on marine mammals
87 (Azzolin et al., 2014; Buscaino et al., 2015; Caruso et al., 2015; Sciacca et al., 2015) or on single
88 species (e.g. crustacean: Buscaino et al., 2011; fish: Picciulin et al., 2013), but information on the
89 characteristics of natural biological sounds of the whole marine assemblages and their variability
90 over time is still extremely limited (Buscaino et al., 2016).

91 In the present study, we provide a first-time assessment for the biological sounds of a rocky
92 bottom coastal area in the Adriatic Sea (central Mediterranean), their daily rhythms, spectral
93 features and variations in two different moments of the year, in order to create a benchmark of the
94 soundscape patterns of the area. These baseline data will allow to provide a background for future
95 investigations against which to measure the effect of anthropogenic impact in the years ahead.

96

97 **2. Material and Methods**

98

99 *2.1 Study Site*

100 Recordings were performed in a selected site of the Adriatic Sea (Italy) facing the Monte Conero
101 Park (43° 34.827' N, 13° 34.635' E). The Adriatic Sea is a large and shallow basin of the central
102 Mediterranean Sea, characterized by a cyclonic general circulation. The mean circulation possesses
103 seasonal variability in response to changing winds and thermal fluxes during the year. The
104 investigated area is characterized by the presence of natural rocky substrates near the coast, which
105 gradually evolve towards sandy bottoms at deeper depths. A high marine biodiversity (Coll et al.,
106 2010) inhabits the area. With the intention of collecting the most complete range of biological

107 sounds, the recording station was located at the end of a natural beam of rock extending for over 1
108 km, named the “Trave”, which offers the unique opportunity to add habitat variability in this region
109 and to investigate its associated high biodiversity. The area provides an ideal substrate for a number
110 of species, including mollusks, crustaceans and fishes, and it is also a feeding ground for some
111 species of cetaceans, such as Bottlenose dolphins (*Tursiops truncatus*) (pers. obs.).

112

113 *2.2 Acoustic data collection*

114 Recordings were conducted over two consecutive days in July (from 2nd to 4th) and September (17th
115 to 19th), 2014. Sampling days were selected to assure calm sea state (<0.30 swell height) and wind
116 speed (< 2 of the Beaufort scale) and to comprehend the peak season for fish sound production,
117 which usually falls in the early summer and overlaps the spawning season (e.g. Bonacito et al., 2001;
118 Connaughton and Taylor, 1995). Recordings were collected using a calibrated omnidirectional DSG
119 acoustic recorder (Loggerhead Instruments), which mounted a HTI96-min hydrophone (High-Tech
120 Inc., Long Beach, MS, USA) with a sensitivity of -179.5 dB re: 1 μ Pa and flat frequency response (+/-
121 0.2 dB) between ~0.1 and 30 kHz. The DSG was set to record continuously from 12 a.m. for 48 hours
122 (80 kHz\16bit\mono with a pre-amplification of -20dB), and to automatically store 1440 one-minute
123 files per day. This recording design aimed at obtaining a faithful soundscape signature and circadian
124 trend of the area, avoiding any possible gap or inference. Consequently, we prioritized the temporal
125 completeness of our data and no temporal sub-sampling was performed. The DSG was deployed
126 through a mooring system on a sandy patch at approximately 10 meters from the end of the rocky
127 beam and kept vertical, with the microphone at about 2 meters from the ground and at 10.5 meters
128 of depth. The mooring system consisted of a vertical pole wedged in a block of concrete, with the
129 DSG tightened at the pole by two brackets to prevent from any movement that could cause
130 production of sounds.

131

132 *2.3 Acoustic data processing*

133 Recordings were visually and aurally scrutinized to detect biological and anthropogenic sounds
134 (Adobe Audition CS6 v.5.0). Using the known calibration and sensitivity of the hydrophone, the
135 detailed distribution of acoustic power across the frequency range of 1–40 kHz was examined by
136 means of power spectral density (PSD) analysis. PSD was calculated on every one-minute file by
137 applying a series of short-term FFT's (50% overlap; FFT size: 2048 points; frequency resolution:
138 39.063 Hz) (Avisoft SASLab Pro, Avisoft Bioacoustics, Germany). Additionally, a software dedicated

139 to soundscape analysis (SoundscapeMeter plug-in, which relies on an open-source software,
140 WaveSurfer©) (Farina et al., 2012) was used to calculate the Acoustic Complexity Index (ACI) (Farina
141 et al., 2011; Pieretti et al., 2011) on the recorded files. This index computes the difference in
142 amplitude of adjacent time samples (milliseconds) in each frequency bin, resulting in high values
143 when analyzing sounds characterized by inner variability over time (typically biophonies) and low
144 values in the presence of constant sounds (such as cars or vessel transits). The ACI was here
145 therefore used as an indicator of biological sounds, in order to separate biological from
146 anthropogenic inputs into the soundscape. Among the acoustic indices recently explored in
147 terrestrial and marine environments, we chose the ACI given the highly touristic and commercial
148 nature of the selected environment and the related noise presence. Previous literature have used
149 the ACI as a metric to track fish vocalizations (Staaterman et al., 2014), shrimp-produced sounds
150 (McWilliam and Hawkins, 2013), species diversity in temperate reefs (Harris et al., 2015), and sounds
151 produced by animal communities in noise-polluted environments (Buscaino et al., 2016; Duarte et
152 al., 2015; Pieretti and Farina, 2013).

153 After a pilot study on a subsample of recordings, we decided to perform two parallel ACI analyses
154 to efficiently describe the principal biological producers of sounds, i.e. fishes (FFT 2048; frequency
155 resolution: 39.063 Hz; temporal resolution: 0.026 secs) and snapping shrimps (FFT 256; 312.5 Hz
156 and 0.0032 secs). This step was intended to give higher resolution to the low frequency bands,
157 where fish vocalizations occur. At an aural screen, fish vocalizations resulted to be constantly lower
158 than 600 Hz, thus we used the $ACI_{FFT\ 2048}$ for the 0-620 Hz frequency range, and the $ACI_{FFT\ 256}$ for
159 frequency bins above 620 Hz. We also added an amplitude filter ($5000\ \mu V^2/Hz$) in the data
160 processing of the higher frequency band (620 Hz- 40 kHz) for considering only the time samples
161 (expressed in milliseconds) in which the amplitude of the signal reached or overpassed the selected
162 threshold, i.e. the louder snaps. The filter allowed preventing biases in acoustic complexity due to
163 the dense presence of snaps in certain moments of the day, which could have been perceived by
164 ACI as a continuous sound and, consequently, filtered out as noise.

165 In order to describe the overall soundscape features and to track their diel rhythms in the two
166 different months, ACI and PSD were represented on 3D interpolation maps using Surfer v 9.0
167 (Golden Software) across the frequency range of 80–20,000 Hz. PSD levels over 620 Hz were
168 compiled into 312 Hz bins to match the ACI settings and to give higher visibility to fish vocalizations
169 at low frequencies. Subsequently, PSD and ACI values were averaged on frequencies (frequency
170 range: 80 Hz – 40 kHz), to obtain the soundscape signature of July and September, and on time

171 (mean \pm SE on one-hour slots), to track the pattern of the hourly circadian rhythm of two frequency
172 bands selected as reference for fish sounds (250 Hz) and snaps (3500 Hz). The 250 Hz reference
173 band was selected with the criterion of intercepting the majority of fish signals, while 3500 Hz was
174 the peak frequency of the snaps. For each month, diel sound variations were determined by
175 comparing mean ACI and PSD values between day and night divided by dawn and dusk (July: 05.30-
176 20.50; September: 06.49-19.11). Hourly means of PSD and ACI at 3500 Hz were used also for
177 assessing eventual variations in snapping activity in concomitance of a prolonged anthropogenic
178 noise recorded in September 18. Recordings of the following day were considered as a control. PSD
179 and ACI at 3500 Hz were successively correlated with PSD at 150Hz (taken as reference band for
180 noise levels) to assess if snaps varied according the intensity of low frequency prolonged noise.
181 When after logarithmic transformation the data distribution remained not normal, non-parametric
182 analyses were performed. The U-Mann Whitney test was used for assessing significant differences
183 between July and September of nightly and daily ACI and PSD. The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for
184 matched pairs was applied for comparing snaps levels during the noisy event and the corresponding
185 minutes of the control day, while a Spearman's rho test was used to correlate noise and snaps levels.
186 All analyses were performed using the Statistica v.8.0 software (StatSoft, 2008).

187

188 *2.4 Sampling of in situ biodiversity*

189 The biodiversity of the site where the recordings were conducted was carried out using Autonomous
190 Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS). The ARMS are composed of stacked PVC settlement plates and
191 are designed to mimic the structural complexity of coral reef habitat (Knowlton et al., 2010). The
192 ARMS have been used to compare invertebrate community compositions among sites as well as to
193 monitor coral reefs (Knowlton et al., 2010). In the present study, three ARMS were installed in the
194 investigated area of the Adriatic Sea at a depth of about 10 m. After one year, the vagile and sessile
195 fauna associated to the structures was identified to the highest taxonomic resolution. Only the
196 species with documented emission of sounds or potential (i.e., at least one known soniferous
197 species within the same genus), are reported in the present study. A checklist provided by local
198 scuba divers allowed the addition of larger-sized or sporadic fish species.

199

200 **3. Results**

201

202 *3.1 Actors and patterns of biological sound sources: aural and visual scrutiny*

203 At an aural and visual inspection of the recordings, we observed high-energy snaps all the day long
204 in both July and September. The snaps peaked at 3500 Hz and were extremely broadband with
205 energy extending from a few hundred Hertz to frequencies above our recording limit (40 kHz). Given
206 the consistency of the sound structure with descriptions found in literature (Versluis et al., 2000), it
207 was possible to attribute these sounds to the snapping shrimp *Alpheus* sp.

208 At frequencies <600 Hz, we registered acoustic signals that were consistent with fish's sound
209 production described in literature (e.g. Malavasi et al., 2008; Picciulin et al., 2013). We recorded
210 sounds characterized by diverse frequency ranges and pulse repetition rates, which suggests the
211 presence of more than one acoustically active fish species. Trains of impulses peaked in nightly
212 hours after the sunset, but were present during the day. In particular, a high production of
213 overlapping signals (chorus) with main energies in the range of 200 - 600 Hz and regular sound
214 patterns were registered from 22.00 to 02.00 in July. Excerpts of spectrograms of typical sounds
215 recorded at the study site are shown in Figure 1s of the Supplementary Materials.

216 The biodiversity analyses conducted at the same site by using ARMS as sampling devices to capture
217 local biodiversity over a year revealed the presence of the following species known to produce
218 sounds: *Alpheus glaber*, *Athanas nitescens*, *Lophozozymus incisus*, *Gobius paganellus*, *Gobius* sp.
219 Additional soniferous species were reported in the checklist provided by scuba-divers: *Dicentrarchus*
220 *labrax*, *Seriola dumerili*, *Sciaena umbra* (rare), *Sparus aurata*, *Chromis chromis* (rare). Other species
221 listed in the site with potential ability to produce sounds were *Penaeus kerathurus*, *Galathea*
222 *strigosa*, *Hippocampus guttulatus*, *Gobius geniporus*, *Parablennius incognitus*, *Symphodus roissali*,
223 *Symphodus tinca*, *Conger conger*, *Balistes carolinensis* (very rare in the area).

224

225 3.2 Soundscape features: Power Spectral Density and Acoustic Complexity Index

226 At lower frequencies, PSD registered sparse events of high acoustic energy related to boat transits
227 mostly during the course of the day and low energies at night (Fig. 1a, c), with a slightly visible
228 increase of levels starting at 22.00 during the chorus in July 2 (Fig. 1a). In contrast, ACI could
229 effectively filter out noise inputs from technophonies although recording high values in
230 correspondence of acoustic impulses of biological origin; at these frequencies, high ACI levels were
231 indeed more frequent at night when most biophonies occurred (Fig. 1b, d). The ACI clearly
232 distinguished a particularly high acoustic complexity during the fish chorus aurally detected (Fig. 1b)
233 but mismatched the peak period, resulting around 24.00 instead of 22.00. At frequencies above 620
234 Hz, we observed high PSD and ACI levels all day long in both months, which were attributed to

235 snapping shrimps' broadband impulses (Fig. 1). However, in specific periods of the day where PSD
236 and ACI levels revealed a particular intensification in snapping activity (e.g., the second night of July),
237 the louder snaps were perceived below 620 Hz and slightly influenced ACI values at the lower
238 frequencies (Fig. 1).

239
240 The power spectral density and complexity distributions below 620 Hz showed opposite tendencies
241 (Fig. 2). PSD had higher levels during the day at both months and was generally characterized by
242 decreasing energies from 100 to 620 Hz. The ACI resulted higher at night, particularly in July, and
243 had a rise in the frequencies from 200 to 400 Hz (Fig. 2). Above 620 Hz, both measures peaked at
244 approximately 3500 Hz and displayed similar patterns of the soundscape signatures and same
245 relative proportions (Fig. 2). Significant differences were observed among all tests performed
246 (Mann-Whitney U test; $p < 0.001$).

247
248 At the high frequency band, consistency between ACI and PSD was also recorded in the circadian
249 patterns (reference band 3500Hz, Fig. 3b, e). Both measures registered considerably increased
250 acoustic energy and complexity at sunset, a gradual decrease until sunrise and a secondary peak at
251 dawn (Figs. 1 and 3b, e). September always presented significantly lower PSD and ACI levels than
252 July (Fig. 3c, f) (Mann-Whitney U test; $p < 0.001$). Circadian patterns at 250 Hz (reference frequency
253 band for fish vocalizations) supported the contrasting output that ACI and PSD showed in the
254 soundscape signature. PSD levels in July were significantly higher than September at day and lower
255 at night (Fig. 3a, c), while ACI presented significant opposite results (Fig. 3d, f) (Mann-Whitney U
256 test; $p < 0.001$).

257
258 A prolonged low-frequency noise was recorded from approximately 04.00 to 09.00 of September
259 18 and involved frequencies below 1 kHz (Fig. 1). A rise in levels was registered by PSD (Fig. 1b) but
260 not by ACI (Fig. 1d). Interestingly, it corresponded to a significant increase of both acoustic energy
261 and complexity of the snaps' peak frequency band (Fig. 4) (Wilcoxon test, $p < 0.001$). ACI and PSD
262 levels at 3500 Hz resulted also to be positively correlated with the intensity of the noise (Spearman's
263 rho, $p < 0.001$; $r_{ACI} = 0,647$; $r_{PSD} = 0,716$).

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265

266

267 **4. Discussion**

268 The Adriatic Sea is shallower than any other regional sea of the Mediterranean basin, it is
269 characterized by a relevant freshwater input and an intense trawling, touristic and shipping activity
270 that contribute to its low water transparency. Investigating marine soundscapes and their changes
271 over time in such these coastal marine environments can provide important insights into the
272 functioning of these systems due to the potentially prevailing role of sounds in the orientation,
273 communication and other ecological processes.

274
275 In the present study, we used power spectral density and a selected acoustic index, the ACI, to
276 analyze the biological sound patterns and to identify the species potentially associated to biological
277 sound production in a selected rocky bottom location. Since during the investigation calm-sea
278 conditions occurred, no significant inputs from geophonies were encountered. The dominant
279 components of the soundscape were the sounds due to snapping shrimps and diverse species of
280 fishes and anthropogenic noise caused by boat transits. Since spectral characteristics of biological
281 sounds varied significantly between July and September, we point out that distinct acoustic
282 signatures are present at different sampling times, likely linked to the temporal dynamics of the
283 biological components generating sounds in the investigated area.

284
285 At frequencies >620 Hz, we found a loud and dense snapping activity due to shrimps of the family
286 Alpheidae, which were also identified in the analysis of biodiversity conducted through the use of
287 Artificial Reef Monitoring Systems deployed in the same area (*Alpheus glaber* and *Athanas
288 nitescens*). The recorded snaps matched the description commonly found in literature: *Alpheus sp*
289 is characterized by transient broadband pulses peaking at 2 to 4 kHz (e.g. McWilliam and Hawkins,
290 2013); *Athanas nitescens* produces signals in the frequency range of 5–11 kHz, here less present
291 (see Coquereau et al., 2016). *A. glaber* represented the major driver of the soundscape dynamics of
292 the area, deeply affecting nearly all frequencies in both recording periods. Previous studies from
293 other biogeographic regions reported that the snapping shrimp dominates hard-bottom
294 soundscapes at frequencies >1000 Hz (Au et al., 2012; Radford et al., 2010; Staaterman et al., 2013).
295 In both sampling periods, an identical circadian rhythm was observed in ACI and PSD, with the
296 presence of snaps all day round, lower values during daylight hours and distinct peaks during sunrise
297 and sunset. Variations between the two months were also detected, with significantly higher PSD
298 and ACI levels in July than September, at night and day. The circadian and seasonal patterns

299 reported in this study are consistent with data from exiting literature (Buscaino et al., 2016;
300 Lammers et al., 2008; Radford et al., 2008), in which snaps have been typically reported to be
301 especially active at dawn and dusk and to increase in the spring and summer and decrease
302 afterwards.

303
304 At lower frequencies, we recorded biological impulses associated to fish vocalizations. These signals
305 typically occurred during the night, but were also present along the daylight hours (see Fig. 1s in the
306 Supplementary Materials for some excerpts of the most commonly recorded signals). Vocalizations
307 of different fish species characterized by diverse frequency ranges and pulse rates were recorded in
308 both sampling months, but unfortunately, the low transparency of the water did not allow the
309 contextual visual census and quantification of the emitters. However, data collected using ARMS
310 indicated that in the investigated period *G. paganellus* and *Gobius* sp. were present in the site of
311 hydrophone deployment. Additionally, the scuba-divers checklist suggested *D. labrax*, *S. dumerili*, *S.*
312 *aurata* and, more rarely, *S. umbra* and *C. chromis* frequent the area.

313 On July 2-3 from 22.00 to 02.00, a particularly high and dense number of signals was recorded
314 repeatedly by several individuals and was attributed to fishes belonging to the family Sciaenidae. In
315 particular, *S. umbra* is considered a rare species, not present in the catch of local fisheries, and is
316 known to generate at night sounds defined as "chorus" (Picciulin et al., 2013). *S. umbra* sounds have
317 been previously recorded in the northern sector of the Adriatic Sea mostly on rocky habitats
318 (Bonacito et al., 2001). The frequency range and pulse repetition reported here are consistent with
319 those reported in the literature for this species.

320
321 Between the two recording periods, we detected variations at the frequency band occupied by
322 fishes. The fish chorus was recorded in July, but not in September, and the ACI revealed significant
323 differences at frequencies <620 Hz between July and September. We found higher ACI levels at night
324 in July, matching the pattern here found for the snapping activity. Similarly, the yearly trends
325 described by previous literature in Mediterranean by Buscaino et al. (2016) reported ACI values at
326 250 Hz to peak in July and gradually decrease along the summer. Several studies described higher
327 sound production in fishes during the late spring and early summer, overlapping with the spawning
328 period (Bonacito et al., 2001; Connaughton and Taylor, 1995). Conversely, ACI values at day
329 suggested a higher bioacoustic activity in September. This result can be due to the diverse habits of
330 different species or to the intense boat traffic recorded during the day in July. Since noise was more

331 pronounced in the frequency bands used by fishes for sound production and hearing, it might be
332 possible that its intensity in July masked biological sounds or discouraged fishes to invest energy in
333 emitting signals that could be hardly forecasted. Further analyses are however needed to evaluate
334 the impact of noise on fish and shrimp sound production and behavior. Nevertheless, as reported
335 in previous studies, low ACI values might be due to the properties of this algorithm to cut sounds
336 with scarce variability of amplitudes over time, as most of the anthropogenic types of noise are
337 (Duarte et al., 2015; Pieretti et al., 2011). The low values of ACI corresponding to the noise might
338 have inhibited ACI values. In this sense, the ACI could be a valid proxy of the health of the
339 environment suggesting quantity and complexity of biological sounds while contemporarily
340 pondering the noise protrusion in the habitats.

341
342 Due to the strong influence on low frequencies of energies linked to the noise introduced by boat
343 transits, the spectral distribution of PSD, its interpolation maps or the circadian graph (reference
344 frequency band: 250 Hz) could not help in identifying reliable cues to locate in time or frequencies
345 fish vocalizations. The amplitudes generated by fish vocalizations were, indeed, hardly recognizable
346 when compared to the energies introduced by shipping. Conversely, the ACI highlighted the
347 chorusing activity in July and tracked the presence of other fish signals all day round, as shown by
348 the bright colors at low frequencies in Figure 1b, d. This discrepancy between the two measures
349 produced a reversed pattern, proportional to the number of noise pollution occurrences, of the
350 soundscape signature (Fig. 2), and of diel circadian rhythms (Fig. 3a, d).

351
352 In correspondence of particularly intense snapping activity, the lower cues of the snaps were
353 recorded at frequencies below 620Hz and, consequently, detected by ACI at low frequencies (Fig.
354 1). We therefore recommend caution in the interpretation of fish sounds determined from ACI in
355 the close proximity to intense snapping activity. In addition, ACI was not able to center the peak
356 period of the fish chorus, since it registered comparatively lower values when vocalizations were
357 dense and overlapped. The contemporary presence of a high number of signals could have produced
358 a consistency of the amplitudes that ACI might have seen as continuous noise. Recently, few studies
359 have tried to apply the ACI and correlate it to biodiversity measurements with contrasting results.
360 For instance, while Kaplan et al (2015) could not find a clear correlation among ACI and fishes
361 assemblages of tropical reefs at Virgin Islands (US), Harris et al. (2015) found ACI to be a reliable
362 metric for describing biodiversity in reef fish communities of temperate sites in north-eastern New

363 Zealand. Additionally, ACI showed a direct correlation with snapping shrimp activity in a protected
364 inlet in Ireland (McWilliam and Hawkins, 2013) and it was found to be a reliable indicator of fish and
365 shrimps signals in Lampedusa, Italy (Buscaino et al., 2016), being it strongly correlated with the
366 effective counts of pulsed biological emissions but not correlated with the geophonic or
367 anthropophonic elements.

368

369 In September, a prolonged noise was detected from 04.00 to 09.00, approximately. Given the
370 constancy and spectral properties of the sound (total energy comprised below 1 kHz) and its high
371 energy levels, this noise had the potential to permeate waters for long distances and to create a
372 massive masking and disturbing effect on marine animals. Interestingly, the noise corresponded to
373 an intensification of the snapping activity, resulting in higher PSD and ACI levels during the noise
374 disturbance (Fig. 4), which were correlated with noise intensity. It might be possible that the
375 increased levels of the snaps represent a response to noise or to the anthropogenic activity linked
376 to its production. Similarly, Spiga (2016) recently recorded a significant increase in the snap number
377 and amplitude during the playback of piling noise, suggesting that loud noise influenced the
378 behavior of these animals.

379

380 **5. Conclusions**

381 Passive acoustic monitoring has been recently suggested as a tool to monitoring ecosystem health
382 and biodiversity, but it requires an understanding of naturally borne acoustic rhythms and
383 connection between sounds and investigated species. As many marine species are now known to
384 emit sounds, we could consider the diversity of sound types as a bioindicator of presence/absence
385 of species and possibly overall community structure (Harris et al., 2015; McWilliam and Hawkins,
386 2013). Long-term investigations in spatially diversified locations are needed, since the interpretation
387 of marine circadian and seasonal acoustical rhythms holds great potentials to support the
388 management of marine natural resources. Our findings suggest that there is a clear spectral and
389 temporal variability of biological sounds in the investigated area. The results of the present study
390 suggest that ACI can effectively help in tracking sounds of the marine biological assemblages, thus
391 representing a promising tool for the routine monitoring of the marine environmental health.

392

393

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399

400

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552 **Figure captions**

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554 Figure 1 – Interpolation maps of PSD and ACI averaged over one-minute recordings along the two
555 recorded days. The ACI maps are the result of two joint analyses performed with different settings
556 (frequency range <620 Hz: FFT 2048; >620 Hz: FFT 256 and noise filter 5000 $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$), which result
557 in different scales of acoustic complexity. PSD was calculated using FFT 2048 (50% overlap). PSD
558 above 620 Hz was compiled in bands of 312 Hz in order to match the ACI graph.

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561 Figure 2 – Average \pm SE spectral distribution of power spectral density and complexity levels, i.e. the
 562 soundscape signature, in July and September. PSD and ACI were averaged over day and night,
 563 divided by dawn and dusk. Frequency bins lower than 620 Hz are highlighted in grey. ACI is the result
 564 of two joint analyses performed with different settings (FFT 2048<620 Hz; FFT 256>620 Hz and noise
 565 filter 5000 μ V²/Hz), which result in different scales of acoustic complexity values. PSD was
 566 calculated using FFT 2048 (50% overlap). For frequencies higher than 620 Hz, PSDs were compiled
 567 into 312 Hz-width frequency bins to match the ACI settings.
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570 Figure 3 – Mean \pm SE power spectral densities (RMSs) (a, b) and complexity levels (ACI) (d, e) at 250
 571 Hz and 3500 Hz (representative frequency bands for fishes' and shrimps' sounds, respectively)
 572 averaged over hour-long intervals. Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare day/night periods
 573 between July and September for the two selected frequency bins (c, f). All tests registered significant
 574 differences at $p < 0.001$ (***)
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577 Figure 4 – Average \pm SE hourly distribution of PSD and ACI at 3500 Hz (reference frequency band for
578 snapping activity), during the low-frequency anthropogenic noise registered from 04:00 to 09:00 in
579 September 18 (dark orange) compared to the following day, September 19 (light orange). All hours
580 registered significantly higher values in the noisy day (Wilcoxon test, $p < 0.001$).

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583 Figure 1s – Examples of anthropogenic and biological sounds typically recurring in the recordings:
584 (a) boat transit; (b) prolonged noise event in September 18; (c) chorus of fishes in July 2;
585 excerpts of other typical signals of biological origin recoded in the sampling location.

586

Fig. 1s

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